

Kinetics and reaction mechanism of the metal ion catalysed hydrolysis of some substituted salicylanils^ψ

D. V. Prabhu^{a*}, K. Lalitha and N. B. Laxmeshwar^b

^aPhysical Chemistry Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Wilson College, Mumbai-400 007, India

E-mail : dvprabhu@rediffmail.com; prabhu_s@vsnl.com Fax : 91-22-3633088

^bPhysical Chemistry Section, Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Mumbai-400 007, India

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A kinetic study of the hydrolysis of the imines, salicylanil, its methyl and chloro derivatives and *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane has been done in the pH range 2.20–12.65 in the temperature range 25–55°C. The comparative rates of hydrolysis are in the sequence, salicylanil > *meta* > *para* > *ortho* and salicylanil > *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane. The synthesis of *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane and its characterisation by IR, NMR and mass has been reported. Suitable reaction mechanisms have been suggested for the hydrolysis in acidic, neutral and basic media based on pK_1 values of the imines, steric hindrance, inductive effect, resonance and mesomeric effects.

The catalytic effect of the transition metal ions, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} on the hydrolysis of the imines has been investigated in detail in the temperature range 30–45°C. The hydrolysis is accelerated as per the sequence Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cu^{II} which is in accordance with the Irving and William's order of stability constants of metal chelates involving nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands. The retardation of the rate at lower Cu^{II} concentrations has been attributed to the Jahn-Teller distortion of the metal-complex to achieve stability.

From the effect of temperature on the rates of hydrolysis of the imines, the thermodynamic activation parameters have been calculated.

The study of the formation and hydrolysis of imines assumes importance due to its close relation to the conversion of >C=O to >C=N and vice versa in biochemical processes^{1–4}. A lot of work has been done on the complexation of metal ions with imines with a view to study the structure and stability of the resulting complexes. There are some reports^{4–10} of the effect of hydrogen, hydroxyl and metal ions on the formation and hydrolysis of a few imines. However, there are very few reports on the kinetic aspects of the hydrolysis of imines.

We report herein

- (i) The kinetics of the hydrolysis of salicylanil and its methyl and chloro derivatives in order to study the effect of substituents on the hydrolysis rate.
- (ii) The catalytic effect of some transition metal ions on the hydrolysis rate of the methyl derivatives of salicylanil.
- (iii) The synthesis and characterisation of the imine, *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane followed by kinetic study of its hydrolysis in the absence and presence of metal ions.

All the data collected has been collated and suitable reaction mechanisms have been suggested based on pK_1 values of imines, inductive effect, resonance and mesomeric effects.

Experimental

(i) *Kinetics of hydrolysis of salicylanil and its derivatives :*

The imines salicylanil (S), *N*-salicylidene-*o*-methyl aniline (A), *N*-salicylidene-*m*-methyl aniline (B), *N*-salicylidene-*p*-methyl aniline (C), *N*-salicylidene-*o*-chloro aniline (D), *N*-salicylidene-*m*-chloro aniline (E) and *N*-salicylidene-*p*-chloro aniline (F) were prepared using methods available in literature. Their structures were confirmed by elemental analysis, IR spectra and m.p. 51°C (S), 40°C (A), 48°C (B), 99°C (C), 82°C (D), 94°C (E) and 102°C (F).

The hydrolysis of the imines was studied spectrophotometrically in a series of universal buffer solutions in the pH range 3.57 to 12.65 in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium in the temperature range 25–55°C. The pH value of the buffer

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

were determined using an Elico-LI-120 digital pH meter. The concentration of the imine was kept at 4×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} and the ionic strength was maintained at $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm^{-3} using 1 M sodium perchlorate (E. Merck). A solution of sodium perchlorate, buffer and ethanol in requisite amounts were allowed to equilibrate in a previously adjusted thermostat (accuracy $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$). The reaction was initiated by adding a known volume of the imine in ethanol which was also maintained at the same temperature. The progress was monitored at $\lambda = 370$ nm (pH < 9) and $\lambda = 420$ nm (pH > 9) (S), $\lambda = 390$ nm (A), $\lambda = 400$ nm (B), $\lambda = 420$ nm (C), $\lambda = 370$ nm (pH < 9) and $\lambda = 420$ nm (pH > 9) (D, E, F) using an Elico Ultra Spec Model C-54 spectrophotometer.

The pseudo first-order rate constants were determined from the linear plots of $\log (A_t - A_\infty)$ vs t .

The protonation/deprotonation equilibria of the imine (HL) may be represented as

where H_2L^+ , HL and L^- represent the protonated, neutral and anionic (due to the deprotonation of the phenolic group of the imine) forms respectively.

$\text{p}K_1$ values were determined by a potentiometric titration of 4×10^{-4} M imine in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at $\mu = 0.1$ M mol dm^{-3} against 0.01 M HCl using a digital pH meter.

[$\text{p}K_1$ values : 4.320 (S), 4.357 (A), 4.498 (B), 4.731 (C), 3.135 (D), 3.255 (E) and 3.817 (F)]

The imine anion (L^-) shows absorption maxima at $\lambda = 390$ nm (A), $\lambda = 400$ nm (B), $\lambda = 421$ nm (C) and $\lambda = 420$ nm (S, D, E and F). $\text{p}K_2$ values were calculated spectrophotometrically in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium and $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm^{-3} .

[$\text{p}K_2$ values : 10.492 (S), 9.709 (A), 9.712 (B), 10.400 (C), 10.466 (D), 9.592 (E) and 9.948 (F)]

(ii) *Kinetics of metal-ion catalysed hydrolysis of salicylanil and its derivatives :*

The hydrolysis was studied at pH = 4.58 under the same conditions as outlined in (i) in the presence of metal ions in the concentration range $[\text{M}^{\text{II}}] = 1$ to 4×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} where $\text{M}^{\text{II}} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Zn^{II} .

(iii) *Synthesis and kinetics of hydrolysis of N,N'-disalicylidene-p,p'-diamino diphenyl methane :*

The imine ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$) was synthesised by refluxing required amounts of salicylaldehyde and *p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane in methanolic medium for 2 h. On cooling, yellow coloured crystals appeared which were separated and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 212°C . The structure was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : C, 79.10; H, 5.70; N, 6.90. Calculated : C, 79.78; H, 5.45; N, 6.89%). IR ν_{max} (KBr, Perkin-Elmer) 1621 (s) (C=N), 3500 (b) (-OH due to inter molecular bonding), 2925 (CH_2), 1600 (sh) (aromatic C-C) and 760.8 (s) cm^{-1} (aromatic C-H); ^1H NMR δ (ppm) 1.5899 (-OH intra molecular hydrogen bonding), 4.0620 ($>\text{CH}_2$), 8.6430 (2(-CH)) and 13.3211 (-OH inter molecular hydrogen bonding) and m/z (M^+) 407. The hydrolysis was studied under identical conditions, as in (i). The rate of hydrolysis in absence and presence of metal ions $\{[\text{M}^{\text{II}}] = 1$ to 6×10^{-4} mol $\text{dm}^{-3}\}$ was followed spectrophotometrically at $\lambda = 345$ nm. $\text{p}K_1$ of the imine was determined as 5.250 and $\text{p}K_2$ as 9.860.

(iv) *Thermodynamic studies of hydrolysis of imines :*

All the hydrolysis reactions were studied in the temperature range 25 – 55°C . From the Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$, the energy of activation and other activation parameters were evaluated.

Results and discussion

Discussion of $\text{p}K_1$ values :

$\text{p}K_1$ values indicate the dissociation of proton from the protonated nitrogen atom of the imine and can even be considered as the proton affinity towards the nitrogen atom of the azomethine linkage.

The $\text{p}K_1$ values of the methyl derivatives of salicylanil follow the sequence, *para* (C) > *meta* (B) > *ortho* (A) > salicylanil. In C, the strong positive effect of the methyl group in *para* position along with the resonance effect of the benzene ring are directed towards the nitrogen atom making it highly basic (high $\text{p}K_1$ value). In B, the positive inductive effect of the methyl group in the *meta* position is relatively less resulting in a lower $\text{p}K_1$ value. In A, the bulky methyl group in *ortho* position offers steric hindrance leading to the rotation of the tolyl ring out of plane of the non-bonding electrons of the nitrogen atom. The interaction of the methyl group with the -OH group of the salicyl part of the molecule also disturbs the planarity of the molecule. The positive inductive effect of the methyl group does lead to the release of electron density to the nitrogen atom but

the mesomeric effect due to resonance is negligible due to the steric hindrance offered by the methyl group. Thus the nitrogen atom in A is least basic and its protonation is hindered. The pK_1 value of A is slightly greater than that of salicylanil due to the positive inductive effect of the methyl group in the *ortho* position.

The pK_1 values of the chloro derivatives of salicylanil follow the sequence, salicylanil (S) > *para* (F) > *meta* (E) > *ortho* (D).

The high pK_1 value of salicylanil indicates high electron density on the nitrogen atom and hence maximum affinity for proton. In F, the negative inductive effect of the chloro group in *para* position and the positive mesomeric effect due to the unshared pair of electrons of the chloro group are responsible for the above sequence of pK_1 values. In E, only the negative inductive effect of the chloro group in *meta* position operates which is more than that in F. In D, the negative inductive effect of the chloro group in *ortho* position is most predominant. In addition, the presence of chlorine atom in the *ortho* position is likely to disturb the planarity of the molecule, thus rendering the positive resonance effect due to resonance almost negligible.

The pK_1 value of *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamine diphenyl methane (5.250) is greater than that of salicylanil (4.320) due to the positive inductive effect of the CH_2 - moiety of the imine molecule.

Rate-limiting pathways :

In the pH range 2.20 to 12.65 the imine (HL) may be assumed to undergo hydrolysis by four rate determining pathways⁹ :

Step (iv) may be eliminated as the rate constant was found to be almost independent of (OH^-) (Tables 1 and 2) hence the overall rate of hydrolysis may be represented as

$$\text{rate} = k_1(H_2L^+) + k_2(HL) + k_3(L^-) \quad (i)$$

In the acidic pH range, the rate constants vary linearly with (H^+) (Tables 1 and 2).

Hence eq. (i) reduces to

$$\text{rate} = k_1(H_2L^+) + k_2(HL)$$

$$k = \frac{k_1}{K_1} (H^+) + k_2$$

The plots of k vs (H^+) were found to be straight lines with zero intercept, hence $k_2 = 0$. k_1 was calculated from the slope of the linear plots.

Table 1. Rate constant data for the hydrolysis of salicylanil and its derivatives

Ethanol-water = 40% (v/v), Temp. = 35°C, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$
 $k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$

pH	$k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$						
	S	A	B	C	D	E	F
3.57	93.02	20.70	71.61	40.30	–	–	–
4.04	56.00	–	–	–	19.59	54.34	36.66
4.36	29.07	6.30	21.13	14.13	10.34	26.23	15.61
4.58	12.37	3.00	10.10	7.30	4.97	12.59	11.03
5.06	5.05	1.10	3.72	3.70	2.63	5.50	4.37
5.42	1.53	0.60	1.41	1.10	0.89	2.00	1.43
6.30	1.18	0.23	0.69	0.90	0.59	1.23	1.12
7.04	0.42	0.30	0.93	0.86	0.14	0.41	0.39
7.95	0.33	–	–	0.69	0.08	0.26	0.31
8.34	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
8.82	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
9.95	–	–	–	3.98	–	–	–
10.76	10.83	–	7.16	11.00	12.04	6.25	7.05
11.75	12.11	–	8.41	11.40	21.79	6.46	9.33
12.39	17.47	3.55	10.23	15.40	24.38	5.96	7.92
12.65	17.22	3.98	10.12	18.10	23.81	7.61	8.00

Reaction mechanism of hydrolysis of imines in acidic and neutral media :

Chart 1 outlines the mechanism of the hydrolysis of the imines in the acidic pH range. The protonation of the nitrogen atom is facilitated by the withdrawal of the electron density on the carbon atom of the C=N bond, leaving it vulnerable to the nucleophilic attack of water. The proton-catalysed attack of water at the reactive imine linkage (k_1) is therefore suggested as the rate determining step.

In the case of the methyl derivatives, the rates follow the sequence, salicylanil (S) > *meta* (B) > *para* (C) > *ortho* (A). In A, the nitrogen atom is less basic due to the steric hindrance offered by the methyl group in the *ortho* position resulting in a very slow nucleophilic attack of water on the electropositive carbon atom. In B, the nitrogen atom is more basic resulting in a faster nucleophilic attack of water. In C, the high basicity of the nitrogen atom hinders the withdrawal

Table 2. Rate constant data for the hydrolysis of salicylanil and *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methaneEthanol-water = 40% (v/v), Temp. = 35°C, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

pH	$k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
	Salicylidene	<i>N,N'</i> -Disalicylidene- <i>p,p'</i> -diamino diphenyl methane
2.20	–	127.00
2.60	230.00	107.00
3.00	182.50	73.30
3.60	107.50	26.80
4.05	56.00	20.80
4.45	20.00	15.10
5.45	1.52	12.00
8.30	–	4.45
8.80	–	4.74
9.80	–	5.25
10.80	8.50	6.68
11.60	12.50	6.65
12.00	14.00	8.21

of electron density from the carbon atom of the imine linkage resulting in a relatively slower nucleophilic attack of water as compared to B. The pK_1 value of salicylanil is least as compared to that of its methyl derivatives hence the withdrawal of electron density from the carbon atom and the subsequent nucleophilic attack of water are greatly facilitated in salicylanil.

In the case of the chloro derivatives, the rates follow the sequence, salicylanil (S) > *meta* (E) > *para* (F) > *ortho* (D). The rate is governed by two steps: (i) protonation of nitrogen atom and (ii) nucleophilic attack of water on carbon atom.

In D, the negative inductive effect of chlorine in *ortho* position decreases the electron density on nitrogen atom leading to slow protonation. This in turn slows down the withdrawal of electron density from the carbon atom and subsequent the nucleophilic attack of water on the electron deficient carbon. In E, the nitrogen atom is more basic leading to a faster rate of hydrolysis as compared to D. In F, the chloro group in the *para* position will have both negative inductive effect and positive mesomeric effect operating simultaneously. But since the mesomeric effect is more, the withdrawal of electron density from the carbon atom will be moderate. Hence, the rate of hydrolysis of F is in between that of D and E. As the pK_1 value of salicylanil is least as compared to its chloro derivatives, its nitrogen atom is least basic. This greatly facilitates the withdrawal of electron

where R =

Chart 1

density from the carbon atom and the subsequent nucleophilic attack of water on the carbon atom. The same holds true for the relative rates of hydrolysis of salicylanil and *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane.

In the neutral pH range, the rates of hydrolysis of all the imines under study are minimum or almost constant. These low rates are attributed to very low catalytic activity of proton resulting in negligible protonation of the imines. The addition of water to the neutral imine $^{10}(k_2)$ is therefore suggested as the rate-determining step.

Reaction mechanism of hydrolysis of imines in basic medium :

Chart 2 outlines the reaction mechanism of the hydrolysis of imines in the basic pH range. The constants are nearly independent of (OH^-) and reach a limiting value at higher (OH^-) values (Table 1). In the basic pH range, the imine may be assumed to be in the anionic form L^- due to the neutralisation of the phenolic proton of the *ortho* hydroxyl group by the OH^- ion of the alkali. In the basic pH range, the imine anion L^- is first formed and goes into resonance resulting in the withdrawal of electron density from the carbon atom of the imine linkage by the nitrogen atom. The nucleophilic attack of water takes place at the resulting electropositive carbon atom. The negative charge on the nitrogen atom is neutralised by the abstraction of H^+ from the water molecule. Thus the slow reaction of water with L^- (k_3)^{9,11} is suggested as the rate-determining step.

For the methyl derivatives, the rates follow the sequence,

Chart 2

salicylanil (S) > *para* (C) > *meta* (B) > *ortho* (A), which is in accordance with the sequence of $\text{p}K_1$ values viz. *para* > *meta* > *ortho* > salicylanil. The highest rate of hydrolysis of salicylanil can be attributed to the least basicity of its nitrogen atom.

For the chloro derivatives, the rates follow the sequence, *ortho* (D) > salicylanil (S) > *para* (F) > *meta* (E) which is in accordance with the sequence of $\text{p}K_1$ values viz. salicylanil > *para* > *meta* > *ortho*.

The highest rate of hydrolysis of D can be explained as follows: the negative inductive effect of chlorine atom in *ortho* position will be predominant on the nitrogen atom and in addition, the planarity of the molecule will be disturbed rendering the mesomeric effect due to resonance almost negligible. The resulting least basicity of the nitrogen atom greatly facilitates the withdrawal of electron density from the carbon atom and the subsequent nucleophilic attack of water on the electropositive carbon atom (in spite of the absorption of H^+ from water being very slow). A comparative study of the rate constant data (Table 1) reveals that in the acidic pH range, the rates follow the sequence, chloro > methyl for all the substituted salicylanils. In the basic range, the sequence is, methyl > chloro for the *meta* and *para* substituted isomers and chloro > methyl for the *ortho* substituted isomers. The higher rate of hydrolysis of salicylanil as compared to that of *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane is also in accordance with the sequence of their $\text{p}K_1$ values.

Metal-ion catalysed hydrolysis of methyl derivatives of salicylanil in acidic pH range :

At $\text{pH} = 4.58$, the hydrolysis follows the sequence, *meta* (B) > *para* (C) > *ortho* (A) in the absence and presence of metal ions. Similarly, at $\text{pH} = 4.05$, salicylanil is hydrolysed faster than *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane. The presence of metal ions accelerates the hydrolysis rate as per the sequence, $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ (Tables 3 and 4).

The imines under study from monocyclic chelates⁵ which are hydrolysed in the presence of metal ions. Imines which form bicyclic chelates⁶ do not hydrolyse under similar conditions. The imines under study have a great tendency to co-ordinate to metal ions as a bidentate ligand through the imine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms¹⁰. Thus it is expected that in the presence of metal ions, the substrate exists mainly in the metal-complex form. Accordingly, the azomethine carbon atom is expected to have high positive charge relative to that in the absence of metal ions

Table 3. Rate constant data for the metal ion catalysed acidic hydrolysis of the methyl derivatives of salicylanil

Ethanol-water = 40% (v/v), pH = 4.58, Temp. = 35°C,
 $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Imine	$[M^{II}] \times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$		
		Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
A (<i>ortho</i>)	In absence	3.00	3.00	3.00
	1	5.20	2.00	4.20
	2	6.53	2.70	5.90
	3	9.50	4.30	8.41
	4	13.50	8.10	11.10
B (<i>meta</i>)	In absence	10.10	10.10	10.10
	1	16.80	6.00	15.14
	2	19.95	6.60	17.18
	3	37.90	10.00	31.00
	4	52.48	14.90	47.50
C (<i>para</i>)	In absence	7.30	7.30	7.30
	1	10.94	6.00	10.80
	2	15.30	6.38	14.29
	3	17.90	9.10	17.60
	4	35.90	14.30	31.60

resulting in a faster nucleophilic attack of water on the carbon atom. The proton catalysed attack of water at the aldimine linkage is therefore suggested as the rate determining step for the hydrolysis of the 1 : 1 metal chelate formed (Chart 3). In the case of imines forming monocyclic chelates, the metal-nitrogen bond weakens the carbon-nitrogen bond making it susceptible to hydrolytic cleavage. Thus, there should be some correlation between the strength of the metal-nitrogen bond and the catalytic ability of the metal ions to hydrolyse the imines. The catalytic effect of the metal ions on the hydrolysis rate can be attributed to the faster decomposition of the carbinolamine intermediate as well as the tendency of the hydrolysis product, salicylaldehyde to co-ordinate to the metal ions.

As seen in Tables 3 and 4, the rates of hydrolysis increase with Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}. But in the case of Cu^{II}, at lower metal ion concentrations, an initial retardation is observed. This may be due to the fact that Cu^{II} with d^9 configuration has unsymmetrical electron distribution in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{z^2} orbitals and is subjected to Jahn-Teller distortion to achieve stability. The observed greater stability of the Zn^{II} complex¹² with respect to Ni^{II} complex is because the metal-ligand bond in the former is purely electrostatic with very little contribution from crystal field stabilisation energy (CFSE). The Zn^{II} ion with smaller size will exert more electrostatic attraction.

Table 4. Rate constant data for the metal ion catalysed acidic hydrolysis of *N,N'*-disalicylidene-*p,p'*-diamino diphenyl methane

Ethanol-water = 40% (v/v), Temp. = 30, 35, 40 and 45°C,
 $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Metal ion	$[M^{II}] \times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$			
		30°C	35°C	40°C	45°C
Ni ^{II}	In absence	18.00	20.85	22.83	24.89
	1	25.40	30.90	36.41	41.67
	2	31.06	38.74	44.17	55.67
	3	40.00	48.60	56.10	66.38
	4	48.10	57.00	68.45	75.99
	5	56.12	64.50	74.95	83.75
Cu ^{II}	In absence	18.00	20.85	22.83	24.89
	1	14.10	15.40	15.92	16.70
	2	16.33	17.00	17.52	18.90
	3	18.92	19.51	21.13	23.52
	4	22.10	24.50	26.80	29.53
	5	24.10	26.13	27.24	31.32
Zn ^{II}	In absence	18.00	20.85	22.83	24.89
	1	21.41	24.71	28.71	32.53
	2	24.67	30.68	34.40	41.73
	3	27.18	32.12	38.41	52.00
	4	31.18	38.40	49.14	60.80
	5	38.41	46.71	58.50	72.38
6	51.00	65.25	72.33	85.12	

The rates of the metal-ion catalysed hydrolysis reactions follow the sequence, Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cu^{II} which can be correlated to the Irving and Williams^{13,14} order of stability constants of transition metal chelates valid, for most nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands viz. Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II}. It is thus evident that the rates of hydrolysis of the imines under study are inversely related to the stability constants of their metal-complexes as well as the electron-withdrawing abilities of the metal ions.

Thermodynamic parameters :

From the effect of temperature (25–55°C) on reaction rate, the energy of activation and related thermodynamic activation parameters have been evaluated. The negative values of ΔS^* indicate that the water molecules are tightly

Chart 3

held at the imine linkage which is the site of hydrolysis. The formation of the activated complex results in an extensive reorientation of water molecules.

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